

An Innovative Approach to Fabricate Wrinkled Silver-Based Nanoporous Materials for SERS Detection

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Abstract : Nanostructured porous surfaces exhibit remarkable properties suitable for a diverse range of applications such as Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS). Nevertheless, the facile engineering of these nanoscale materials is constrained by the limitations inherent to the current synthesis methodologies employed for their fabrication. In this work, we present an innovative plasma-derived technique for the fabrication of silver-based nanoporous wrinkled surfaces. First, by depositing a magnetron-sputtered Ag-Al thin film onto a liquid plasma polymer film (PPF), we exploit the spontaneous wrinkling phenomenon that occurs in bilayer systems composed of a soft and stiff layer. Notably, the thickness of the PPF influences the nanowrinkle amplitude (ranging from 280 nm to 520 nm) while the wavelength remains constant (approximately 2 μm). This behavior is attributed to the pinning of the metal layer to the silicon substrate. Then, the wrinkled surface is further nanostructured by dealloying, which involves the etching from the less noble element of the alloy, here aluminum, resulting in the formation of a silver-based nanoporous structure that retains the wrinkled morphology. An increase in dealloying time, while increasing the nanopore dimensions, results in a loss of wrinkle amplitude, which can be explained by the shrinking of the metal layer during the dealloying process, leading to tensile strain. Our results clearly demonstrate the attractiveness of this innovative method for fabricating wrinkled nanoporous materials with customizable dimensions. Furthermore, this substrate applicative potential as a SERS platform has been evaluated considering the rhodamine B molecule, demonstrating a detection limit of 10^{-9} M.

KEYWORDS. Wrinkling; Dealloying; Plasma Polymerization; Nanoporous Wrinkled Material; Magnetron Sputtering; Tunable Dimensions; Silver Nanostructure; SERS

Introduction

Over the past few decades, there has been a growing interest in nanoporous surfaces within the scientific community due to their unique characteristics, including high surface area, low density, and exceptional flexibility. These characteristics make them highly versatile, enabling their application across various fields such as optics,^{1,2} catalysis,³ biotechnologies,⁴ and flexible electronics.^{5,6} To meet the demand for these materials, numerous synthesis methods have been developed, including metal deposition in templates,^{7,8} galvanic replacement,^{9,10} and dealloying.^{11,12} Among these, dealloying stands out for its versatility, simplicity and reproducibility.

Recent studies have highlighted the potential of combining wrinkling with nanoporous surfaces to further enhance their properties and broaden their range of applications. This dual nanostructuration enables further optimization of key features such as surface area, flexibility, and hotspot properties, which are crucial for achieving high Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) efficiency. Notably, several studies have reported SERS enhancements ranging from 8- to 100-fold for wrinkled nanoporous gold and silver substrates compared to their planar counterparts.¹³⁻¹⁵ These nanostructures also find applications in the fabrication of superhydrophobic surfaces¹⁶ and biosensors.¹⁷ However, despite these promising applications, the synthesis of such complex nanostructured surfaces faces significant challenges. Typically, wrinkled nanoporous surfaces are created by

depositing a nanoporous film onto a thermally shrinkable substrate, such as pre-strained polystyrene. Subsequent heating of this bilayer system induces the substrate to shrink resulting in the formation of wrinkles via buckling.^{13,15} While this fabrication method is effective, the heating process and the need for thermally shrinkable substrates limit the broader application of these promising materials.

Recently, our group has established a novel and flexible method for the fabrication of nanowrinkled surfaces with tunable dimensions.¹⁸⁻²¹ This nanostructuring methodology exploits the spontaneous wrinkling occurring in bilayer systems consisting of a viscous plasma polymer film and a magnetron-sputtered aluminum layer. It was demonstrated that flexible thin-film electronics could be efficiently designed following this approach, paving the way for plasma-based applications in research domains such as stretchable solar cells.¹⁸

In this context, by combining plasma deposition processes and dealloying, we propose an innovative strategy for fabricating silver-based wrinkled nanoporous surfaces of particular interest for SERS-based detection.^{13,15} Our approach, illustrated in Figure 1, begins with the deposition of a high-viscosity liquid plasma polymer film (PPF) from allyl alcohol,²² leveraging the benefits of plasma polymerization, including low environmental impact due to the absence of solvents in the synthesis procedure, excellent adhesion properties of the coatings on all kinds of substrates and industrial scalability of the technique.²³⁻²⁷

Figure 1. Schematic description of the research strategy developed in this study: (1) Synthesis of a liquid PPF on a silicon substrate; (2) deposition of a silver-aluminum alloy layer by co-magnetron sputtering and (3) dealloying of the alloy layer through exposure to gaseous HCl.

In the next step, a thin Ag-Al alloy layer is deposited on top of the polymeric material using another plasma-based technique, namely magnetron co-sputtering. The resulting bilayer system is expected to spontaneously develop a wrinkled surface as previously reported for pure Al thin films.^{18,19,21,28}

Finally, the wrinkled alloy-based material undergoes dealloying with HCl in the vapor phase to selectively dissolve the less noble element (i.e. aluminum), resulting

in a three-dimensional nanoporous structure made of silver (step 3 of Figure 1).

Although dealloying is more commonly performed in the liquid phase, recent studies have shown that vapor dealloying can help reduce delamination and agglomeration issues.^{29,30}

In this work, we investigate the morphological evolution of the resulting nanostructured material and discuss the fundamental phenomena involved in wrinkling and dealloying. Specifically, we examine how the dimensions of the wrinkles affect the nanoporosity of the coating and how the nanopores' and wrinkles' dimensions change during the dealloying process. Additionally, we evaluate properties relevant to practical applications of these nanostructured coatings, such as the surface chemical composition. Finally, the applicative potential of the material as a SERS platform for rhodamine B detection is demonstrated.

Experimental section

Throughout the manuscript, “layer” refers to a thin film, while “bilayer” denotes a material composed of two thin films of different compositions.

Plasma Polymer Film Synthesis. Plasma polymer films were deposited using a metallic deposition chamber (65 cm in length and 35 cm in diameter) with a residual pressure of less than 2×10^{-6} Torr. A combination of turbomolecular and primary pumps was used to evacuate the chamber. A more detailed description of the plasma chamber can be found elsewhere.³¹ The reactor is fitted with an internal water-cooled, one-turn inductive copper coil (100mm in diameter) connected to a radio-frequency (13.56 MHz) power supply (from Advanced Energy) with a matching network. The dissipated power and precursor flow rate for all the experiments were 40W and 10sccm, respectively. The distance separating the substrate from the coil was fixed at 100 mm. The working pressure of 40 mTorr was controlled during the process with a throttle valve connected to a capacitive gauge. The substrate temperature was precisely maintained at 0 ± 1 °C by liquid nitrogen flow in the manipulator (for cooling) and electrical resistances integrated into the substrate holder (heating). A thermocouple embedded within the substrate holder ensured accurate temperature regulation. Before each deposition, the substrate temperature was stabilized for 30 minutes to ensure the thermal equilibrium between the silicon substrate and the heating/cooling system. The deposition time was calibrated to obtain a thickness of 250 nm.

2-Propen-1-ol (99%, Sigma-Aldrich), referred to as allyl alcohol, was used as received for the deposition of PPF on $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ silicon wafers. Before their introduction into the plasma chamber, the substrates were cleaned with 1-isopropanol three times and dried under a nitrogen flow.

The choice of the bottom layer synthesis parameters is motivated by a previous work investigating the influence of the substrate temperature on the mechanical properties of plasma polymers based on allyl alcohol.²² Although PPF are usually described as a three-dimensional polymeric network characterized by the absence of repeating units and hard elastic properties, it was demonstrated that coatings synthesized at a low substrate temperature (i.e. 10°C or lower) present a low cross-linking degree and a viscous-like behaviour, with an associated viscosity estimated at around 10 Pa.s. XPS analysis reveal an atomic oxygen content of $\sim 19\%$.

Deposition of Ag-Al alloy thin film. The synthesis procedure for the thin Ag-Al alloy layer was adapted from previous work.³⁰ The Ag-Al alloy thin films were deposited using DC magnetron co-sputtering in a pure argon plasma, with co-focally arranged Ag and Al targets (both 50 mm in diameter and 99.99% purity). The residual pressure was maintained at less than 1.2×10^{-6} Torr, and the working pressure was kept at 5mTorr using a throttle valve connected to a capacitive gauge. The electrical power applied to the Ag and Al targets was set at 50W and 150W, respectively. The substrate was positioned at 180 mm from the targets, and the angle between the magnetron source axis and the normal to the substrate was 30° . The substrate holder would rotate at a rate of 1.6 rpm to ensure a homogeneous deposition. The

deposition time was fixed at 150, 300, and 450 seconds to ensure an alloy film thickness of 50, 100 and 150 nm, respectively.

Dealloying. Gas-phase dealloying was performed by placing the sample in a crystallizing dish at a distance of 5 cm from the concentrated HCl solution (36 wt%). The system was then closed with a watch glass, ensuring a saturating vapor pressure of HCl. The sample was removed and immersed in demineralized water for 1 minute to stop dealloying and ensure a good cleaning.

AFM measurements. Topographical analysis of the multilayer system was carried out with a Bruker Multimode 8 microscope (Tapping Mode) associated with a Nanoscope III controller. The obtained 256 points × 256 points images were treated with the section tool of "Nanoscope Analysis 3" software to determine the average wavelength and amplitude of the wrinkles.

For both the PPF and the alloy, thicknesses were acquired by scratching the coating surface with a scalpel blade and measuring the depth of the produced step using AFM measurement with the same apparatus.

SEM images. Nanopore dimensions were evaluated with the help of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). SEM micrographs were obtained with a HITACHI STEM-FEG at an acceleration voltage of 5 kV. The images were treated with the ImageJ software to assess nanopore size. For each sample, the sizes of 50 nanopores were measured and recorded for statistical analysis.

XPS measurements. The chemical composition of the samples has been investigated through XPS (X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy). The measurements

were carried out by a VersaProbe apparatus under a pressure of 5×10^{-9} Torr. The photon source was a monochromatized Al K α line (1486.6 eV). The emitted photoelectrons were collected at an angle of 45° to the surface. High-resolution Ag3d and Al2p spectra were curve fitted using Multi-Pak software, considering a Doniach-Sunich function with an asymmetry parameter α and a convolution width of respectively 0.001 and 450 for the metallic silver, metallic aluminum and the Ag $_x$ Al $_y$ alloy peaks or a Gaussian-Lorentzian function (70% Gaussian) for the aluminum and silver oxide. The peak FWHM was between 0.8 and 1.2 for the Doniach-Sunich and between 0.8 and 1.9 for the Gaussian-Lorentzian functions.

XRD analysis. The film's crystallographic structure was investigated through X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique using the Cu K α as an X-ray source. The measurements were performed with an Empyrean XRD instrument supplied by Panalytical at a grazing angle of 10°.

Surface-enhanced Raman Scattering measurements. Raman spectra were recorded using a Senterra Bruker micro-Raman spectrometer with a 532 nm excitation laser line and a power of 0.2 mW. The samples were immersed for 24 hours into an ultrapure water solution of rhodamine B (RhB) with concentration values varying from 10^{-6} to 10^{-10} mol.L $^{-1}$ and dried in air for 4 hours. Raman spectra were recorded on six different area of each sample to ensure the homogeneity of the SERS response.

Results and Discussion

In the first attempt, an Ag-Al alloy thin film with a thickness varying from 50 nm to 150 nm was deposited on a viscous PPF. The following notation is used to differentiate these samples : a bilayer system with an alloy layer of thickness “X” nm is denoted as w-AgAl-“X”nm. The same sample after dealloying is denoted as wNP-Ag-“X”nm.

From the analysis of the XPS survey presented in Figure S1, aluminum and silver elements are clearly identified with an Al/Ag ratio of 1.5. Furthermore, oxygen and carbon are also detected due to surface contamination. Fitting the Ag 3d and Al 2p peaks provides evidence of the formation of an Ag-Al alloy and surface oxidation (see Figure S2). The crystalline structure of the as-grown material is examined using X-ray diffraction, indicating the crystalline nature of the films (see Figure S3).

Figure 2 depicts the corresponding top-view SEM images of the layered systems, illustrating the spontaneous occurrence of the wrinkling phenomenon, which has been previously observed for pure Al deposition on similar underneath layers.^{18,19,21,28} A high-magnification image of the w-AgAl-100nm sample (Figure 2d) shows the granular structure observed over the whole alloy layer, as previously reported in another study on the magnetron sputtering of Ag-Al.³²

Figure 2. Top-view SEM images showing the morphology of (a) the w-AgAl-50nm sample; (b) the w-AgAl-100nm sample; (c) the w-AgAl-150nm sample; and (d) high magnification SEM image of the w-AgAl-100nm sample highlighting the grain-like structure observed over the whole wrinkled surface.

To quantitatively investigate the evolution of the wrinkle dimensions with the thickness of the top layer, AFM measurements were performed and are presented in Figure 3. The wrinkle amplitude (peak-to-valley distance, A) increases from 280 ± 70 nm to 520 ± 230 nm as the thickness of the Ag-Al layer increases, while the wavelength (peak-to-peak distance, λ) remains constant (i.e., $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ considering the confidence intervals).

Considering a conventional viscoelastic polymeric fluid covered by a thin metallic film, a theoretical model has been established taking into account the compression

elastic and bending energy of the top layer as well as the elastic energy of the bottom polymeric coating. Minimizing the total energy yields Equation 1 governing the wrinkle dimensions:^{33,34}

$$\lambda \sim (h \times H)^{\frac{1}{2}}(E_M/E_P)^{\frac{1}{6}} \quad (1)$$

Where h and H represent the top and bottom layer thicknesses, and E_M and E_P represent the Young moduli of the alloy layer and the PPF coating, respectively.

For a constant strain, a linear correlation between the wrinkle amplitude and wavelength can be established:²¹

$$\delta_c \sim (A/\lambda)^2 \quad (2)$$

Where δ_c represents the compressive strain.

Considering Equation 1 and Equation 2, we can correlate the amplitude evolution with the layers' thicknesses and mechanical properties:¹⁸

$$\lambda \sim \frac{A}{\sqrt{\delta_c}} \sim (h \times H)^{\frac{1}{2}}(E_M/E_P)^{\frac{1}{6}} \quad (3)$$

Figure 3. Topographic AFM images of (a) the w-AgAl-50nm sample; (b) the w-AgAl-100nm sample and (c) the w-AgAl-150nm sample. (d) shows a cross-section of Figure 4b.

The evolution of the wrinkle amplitude and wavelength derived from the analysis of the AFM images in Figure 3a-c is plotted as a function of $(h \times H)^{1/2}$ (Figure 4). Although the amplitude aligns well with Equation 3, the wavelength remains constant with respect to $(h \times H)^{1/2}$.

Figure 4. Evolution of (a) the wrinkle wavelength and (b) amplitude as a function of $(h \times H)^{1/2}$.

Remarkably, a previous study on Cr films deposited through magnetron sputtering on silicone oil drops reported a similar phenomenon: for a given distance from the drop edge, an increase in the metal layer thickness leads to an increase in amplitude but does not affect the wavelength of the nanostructures.³⁵ This surprising behavior was attributed to the constrain at the edge of the drop (i.e., the interaction between the metallic layer and the substrate), which would stop the development of the wavelength. Considering bilayer systems similar to the one investigated in this work, several studies have demonstrated a significant pinning phenomenon, where the metallic layer comes into close proximity with the substrate, allowing for interaction during surface reorganization, which ultimately leads to the immobilization of the system.^{18,36} In a previous investigation from our group, this substrate pinning was highlighted by SEM edge images for bilayer systems designed with a viscous liquid PPF layer and an Al-based top layer.¹⁸

Given the literature and our wrinkle dimensions, we can reasonably expect the system to be constrained by the pinning of the top layer to the silicon substrate, resulting in behavior similar to that reported for Cr films deposited on oil drops (i.e., the variation of the amplitude while the wavelength remains constant).³⁵

It is important to note that the wrinkling phenomenon is driven by compressive forces (such as those arising from mismatches in thermal expansion coefficients or inherent to the thin film deposition methods) acting on a rigid thin layer overlying an elastic or viscous material, leading to surface reorganization.^{33,34} The presence of compressive intrinsic stress in metallic films has been widely reported in magnetron sputtering methods and is usually ascribed to adatom insertion into grain boundaries.^{37,38} Furthermore, during metal deposition, exothermic surface condensation reactions as well as ionic bombardment could lead to a spontaneous increase in the system temperature. After deposition and as a consequence of the significantly different thermal expansion coefficient of the metal and the polymeric coating, additional compressive stress would be also generated.^{21,34} Consequently, out-of-plane bending of the metallic layer occurs to accommodate this strain. However, bending of the metal coating is limited by the elastic deformation of the bottom layer, resulting in wrinkle formation.

It is then plausible that the wrinkling phenomenon and the pinning effect occur during the deposition process, freezing the wrinkle wavelength as the alloy coating interacts with the silicon substrate. The amplitude of the wrinkles would still

increase as the thickness of the top layer increase, as observed in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

To fabricate a wrinkled silver-based nanoporous material (denoted wNP-Ag-“X”nm, where X is the thickness of the deposited alloy layer), the samples are then exposed to HCl vapors for different durations and subsequently rinsed in deionized water. For the wNP-Ag-50nm sample, the dealloying procedure results in the delamination of the layer, as confirmed by XPS analysis which shows no evidence of aluminum or silver on the dealloyed surface (see Figure S4). For a top layer thickness of 100 nm and 150 nm, the SEM images (Figure 5) show the formation of nanopores after the dealloying process as compared to the pristine samples (Figure 5a and e). Both samples show a similar morphological evolution as the dealloying time increases. Dealloying for 30 minutes (Figure 5b and 5f) leads to a non-homogeneous etching of the alloy, with different regions of the sample showing significant discrepancies in nanopore density. A compact layer covers certain regions of the surface: this phenomenon has been documented in previous studies involving similar alloy compositions and is attributed to the precipitation of AgCl occurring on the metallic surface during the dealloying process.^{12,30,39,40} After 60 minutes of HCl exposure (Figure 5c and 5g), the nanopore distribution across the metallic surface becomes more homogeneous, although their dimensions remain relatively unchanged. Further increasing the dealloying time to 120 minutes (Figure 5d and 5h) results in a notable increase in nanopore dimensions, accompanied by a corresponding increase in the ligament thickness.

Figure 5. Top-view SEM images showing the morphological evolution of wrinkled bilayer systems as a function of dealloying time in gaseous HCl. Two surfaces are studied here: (a-d) wNP-Ag-100nm and (e-h) wNP-Ag-150nm. The first row (a and e) correspond to SEM images of the sample before dealloying. The second (b and f),

third (c and g), and fourth (d and h) rows correspond to a dealloying time of 30, 60, and 120 minutes, respectively.

From the SEM images, the mean pore dimensions, i.e. their mean length and width, have been measured (see Figure 6). The complete distributions of the wNP-Ag-150nm pore dimensions are presented in Figure S5. As shown in Figure 6, for both systems and considering the margin error, no significant change in nanopore dimensions is observed for samples dealloyed for 30 minutes and 60 minutes (i.e. width around 20 nm and length around 40 nm). This stagnation is likely due to the formation of an AgCl passivation layer which prevents the remaining metallic Al from reacting with HCl, as discussed previously.^{12,30,39,40} After 120 minutes of dealloying, it can be inferred that this layer cracks down, allowing further etching and consequently leading to a significant increase in the nanopore formation (Figure 6d and 6h). Specifically, the nanopore length increases from 44 ± 18 nm to 186 ± 69 nm for the wNP-Ag-100nm sample and from 36 ± 14 nm to 110 ± 51 nm for the wNP-Ag-150nm sample, while their width increases from 25 ± 5 nm to 70 ± 27 nm and from 24 ± 8 nm to 51 ± 20 nm respectively. Considering SERS applications, it should be mentioned that nanopores dimensions typically below 50 nm are reported to provide a significantly higher Raman signal, making the nanoscale samples dealloyed for 60 minutes or less well-suited for this analysis method.⁴¹

Figure 6. Influence of the dealloying time on the mean nanopore lengths and widths of (a) the wNP-Ag-100nm sample and (b) the wNP-Ag-150nm sample.

To investigate the dealloying kinetics, the chemical composition was monitored as a function of the etching duration. The corresponding XPS survey spectra are illustrated in Figure 7. Notably, for dealloying durations of 30 and 60 minutes, Cl is distinctly identified, confirming the formation of the AgCl passivation layer as previously mentioned. However, after 120 minutes of dealloying, Cl is no longer observed in the spectrum, suggesting that the AgCl layer has been removed. This mechanism is further confirmed by examining the evolution of the Al/Ag ratio with increasing dealloying time (see Figure S6).

Figure 7. XPS survey spectra for the wNP-Ag-100nm bilayer system dealloyed with gaseous HCl for 0 minutes (in red), 30 minutes (in black), 60 minutes (in blue) and 120 minutes (in green).

As evidenced by Figure S6, during the initial 30 minutes of dealloying, the Al/Ag ratio exhibits an abrupt decrease (i.e., from 1.5 to 0.27) as most of the aluminum reacts with the HCl molecules to form AlCl₃. The latter is then removed from the surface during the cleaning step. However, when the etching time is extended to 60 minutes, the Al/Ag ratio remains nearly constant compared to 30 minutes, with a value of around 0.33. Finally, a significant change is observed for the 120-minute dealloyed sample as the Al/Ag ratio drops to 0.03. This is attributed to the formation of an AgCl passivation layer at an early stage of the dealloying process, which restricts the diffusion of HCl molecules in the material until the AgCl passivation layer is

disrupted for the 120-minute dealloyed samples, thereby facilitating the leaching of nearly all Al atoms in the alloy.

AFM investigations examine the progression of wrinkles' dimensions as a function of dealloying duration (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Topographic AFM images of wrinkled Ag-Al alloy layer for various dealloying time: (a and e) 0 minutes, (b and f) 30 minutes, (c and g) 60 minutes, and (d and h) 120 minutes. The top row (a-d) corresponds to an initial alloy thickness of 100 nm (i.e., sample wNP-Ag-100nm), while the bottom row corresponds to an alloy thickness of 150 nm (i.e., sample wNP-Ag-150nm).

For both systems, the amplitude of the wrinkles diminishes during the dealloying process, ultimately resulting in the complete absence of wrinkles for the wNP-Ag-100nm sample after 120 minutes of HCl exposure (see Figure 8d). As illustrated in

Figure 9, the amplitude A decreases from 410 ± 150 nm to 221 ± 64 nm after 60 minutes of dealloying for the wNP-Ag-100nm sample. Similarly, for the wNP-Ag-150nm sample, A decreases from 520 ± 230 nm to 160 ± 50 nm after 120 minutes of dealloying. In contrast, the wavelength remains constant for both bilayer systems, at approximately $2 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 9. Variation of the wavelength (red) and amplitude (blue) as a function of the dealloying time for (a) the wNP-Ag-100nm sample and (b) the wNP-Ag-150nm sample.

It should be noted that, since the plasma polymer film is a high-viscosity fluid,²² no elastic energy is conserved in the bottom layer. Consequently, it can be reasonably expected that the driving force for the observed morphological change originates from the top metallic layer and the dealloying process.

Several studies have documented significant material shrinkage during the dealloying of AuAg or AuCu alloys, with a relative size loss of up to 13%.^{42–44} This phenomenon is typically attributed to plastic deformation resulting from the motion

of dislocations, as a high defect density is observed when significant shrinking occurs.^{42,45} Since this phenomenon is three-dimensional, shrinking parallel to the substrate can be expected along with thickness loss, leading to tensile stresses and strains in the metallic layer. As a result, the amplitude of nanostructures would decrease during the dealloying process, while the wavelength would remain constant due to the pinning of the metal layer to the substrate. For a long dealloying time, total amplitude loss results in the formation of a planar nanoporous surface, as observed in the wNP-Ag-100nm samples dealloyed for 120 minutes.

Additionally, to assess the applicative potential of the obtained nanostructured films, further characterization was performed by analyzing the Ag 3d peak region in the XPS spectra (Figure S7).

For the dealloyed samples, a notable shift towards lower binding energy values is observed with increasing dealloying time. This behavior is likely related to the dimensional evolution of the ligaments during the dealloying process, as previously reported for nanoparticles and nanoporous surfaces.^{30,46} Additionally, the presence of a loss feature characteristic of metallic silver was detected in the Ag 3d XPS spectra of the dealloyed samples, suggesting that this material is well-suited for various applications including Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS)¹⁵ and electrochemical sensing.¹⁷ Moreover, the metallic nature of the silver material is also confirmed by XRD analysis (see Figure S8).

Finally, the SERS response of the material for the detection of rhodamine B (RhB) molecules has been evaluated. Figure S9 presents Raman spectra of the RhB

diluted at 10^{-6} mol.L⁻¹ recorded for a wrinkled alloy system (i.e. w-AgAl-100nm) and a nanoporous wrinkled silver surface, namely wNP-Ag-100nm sample dealloyed for 60 minutes. No Raman signal was detected for the wrinkled alloy sample since the structure is composed mostly of aluminum and does not present a plasmonic resonance. For the dealloyed surface, an intense Raman spectrum of RhB is recorded, highlighting the SERS effect of the nanoporous wrinkled silver-based material.

In order to evaluate the detection limit of RhB for our sample, the SERS response of the dealloyed sample was evaluated considering a RhB solution diluted at 10^{-6} mol.L⁻¹, 10^{-7} mol.L⁻¹, 10^{-8} mol.L⁻¹, 10^{-9} mol.L⁻¹ and 10^{-10} mol.L⁻¹ (Figure 10). A Raman signal of rhodamine B is observed for a solution down to 10^{-9} mol.L⁻¹ and completely disappears at 10^{-10} mol.L⁻¹. Thus, the experimental detection limit for our nanostructured material can be considered to be a concentration of 10^{-9} mol.L⁻¹, corresponding to the maximum allowable residue limit for RhB in food fixed by the European Union standard (1.04×10^{-9} mol.L⁻¹).⁴⁷

Figure 10. Raman spectra recorded after 24 h of immersion in a rhodamine B solution for different concentrations for a wNP-Ag-100nm sample dealloyed for 60 minutes.

Conclusion

This work introduces an innovative approach for fabricating silver-based wrinkled nanoporous materials through plasma processes and by combining the wrinkling phenomenon with the dealloying technique.

Initially, a bilayer system is designed by depositing a silver-aluminum alloy layer onto a viscous liquid PPF. The spontaneous morphological reorganization of these plasma-fabricated samples results in the formation of nanowrinkles on the surface. The wrinkle amplitude was found to increase with the alloy layer thickness (i.e., from 280 ± 70 nm to 520 ± 230 nm) while the wrinkle wavelength remains constant at approximately 2000 nm. This behavior is attributed to the pinning effect of the nanowrinkles on the silicon substrate.

Further nanostructuring is achieved via dealloying, where the selective removal of aluminum using gaseous HCl produces a nanoporous silver surface. The pore size can be tuned by adjusting the dealloying duration. XPS and XRD analysis confirm the formation of metallic silver. The dealloying process also impacts the wrinkles' amplitude which decreases due to tensile strain induced by the contraction of the metallic layer upon HCl exposure.

Finally, the SERS properties of the nanoporous material were evaluated considering rhodamine B as a probe molecule, for which a limit of detection of 10^{-9} mol.L⁻¹ was demonstrated.

This synthesis method enables the straightforward fabrication of customized nanoporous silver-based wrinkled films with potential applications in optics,

biosensing, and superhydrophobic surfaces. Furthermore, due to the excellent adhesion properties of plasma polymer, this approach can potentially be applied to all kinds of substrate. The minimal processing steps, versatility, and inherent advantages of plasma techniques, such as industrial scalability and environmental friendliness, further highlight the high potential of this approach.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting information. Additional experimental data, including XPS spectrum before dealloying, high-resolution peaks of Ag 3d and Al 2p, XRD patterns of wrinkled samples before and after dealloying, XPS spectrum illustrating surface delamination, pore size distribution, the variation of the aluminum to silver ratio as a function of the dealloying time and Raman spectra correlating the SERS properties of the silver-based material (PDF). This material is available free of charge.

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The manuscript was written with the contributions of all authors. All authors have approved the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

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ABBREVIATIONS

BE, Binding Energy; PPF, Plasma Polymer Film; w-AgAl-"X"nm, Wrinkled film with an initial alloy layer thickness of "X" nm; wNP-Ag-"X"nm, Wrinkled NanoPorous film with an initial alloy layer thickness of "X" nm; RhB, Rhodamine B

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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Silver-based Material**

